

Breast Density Classification using Local Septenary Patterns: A Multi-resolution and Multi-Topology Approach

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Abstract—We present an extension of our previous work in [1] by investigating the use of Local Septenary Patterns (LSP) for breast density classification in mammograms. The LSP operator is a variant of Local Binary Patterns (LBP) inspired by Local Ternary Patterns (LTP) and Local Quinary patterns (LQP). The main extensions in our work are i) we investigate the use of a multi-resolution technique when extracting micro texture information, ii) we investigate different neighbourhood topologies as different ways of extracting texture features, and iii) we use an additional dataset called InBreast as well as the most popular dataset in the literature, which is the Mammographic Image Analysis Society (MIAS) to further evaluate the performance of the LSP operator.

Keywords—Breast Density Classification, Mammography, Local Binary Patterns, Local Ternary Patterns, Local Septenary Patterns, Computer Aided Diagnosis

I. INTRODUCTION

Breast cancer is the most common types of cancer in women. Breast Cancer UK revealed that over 11,000 women died in the United Kingdom (UK) in 2016 [2]. For women who have more dense breast tissue the similarity in appearance of tumour and normal tissue make it difficult to detect tumour in mammograms. During the screening procedure, breast density is assessed visually by radiologists and classified into four groups based on the amount of dense tissue. The Breast Imaging-Reporting and Data System (BI-RADS) fourth edition is one of the guidelines used in breast density assessment based on the amount of dense tissue: i) BI-RADS I (0-25%), ii) BI-RADS II (26-50%), iii) BI-RADS III (51-75%) and iv) BI-RADS IV (over 75%).

Although visual assessment can be done by radiologists, this task is often suffers from variability between radiologists and time-consuming. For example, radiologists with more experience tend to produce more consistent results than less experienced radiologists. Moreover, visual assessment could lead to false negatives/positives due to fatigue during diagnostic decision-making and influence the final outcome. Figure 1 shows examples of four breasts with their associated BI-RADS classes. In this study we use the fourth edition of BI-RADS because all datasets are annotated for ground truth based on this edition.

Figure 1. An illustration of breast density according to the BI-RADS guideline fourth edition taken from the InBreast dataset.

CAD systems have the potential to automatically estimate the amount of dense tissue within the patient’s breast without intervention by a radiologist. In the last decades, many CAD systems for breast imaging have been developed, and the majority of them used texture information to investigate the appearance in order to estimate the amount of dense tissue. This paper investigates the effects of multi-resolution a technique and different neighbourhood topologies such as ellipse, parabola and hyperbola in addition to the conventional topology used in local pattern feature extraction, which is a circle.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In an early study, an interactive thresholding technique was used [10]. This technique requires a user to manually tuning the grey-level threshold value within the regions contain dense tissue. Other methods [4], [5], [6], [7] are based on the first and second-order statistical features. Histogram-based texture such as local binary patterns (LBP) were employed in the study of Chen *et al.* [8] and Bosch *et al.* [9] and Textons were used by Chen *et al.* [8], Bosch *et al.* [9] and Petroudi *et al.* [11].

Chen *et al.* [8] reported different accuracies of 59%, 70%, 75% and 72% using different local patterns such as LBP, Texton, basic image features (BIF) and local grey-level appearance (LGA), respectively. Later, a topographic representations technique by modelling the distribution of the dense region was developed and reported an accuracy of 76%. In a Texton-based approach, Petroudi *et al.* [11] employed the Maximum Response 8 (MR8) filter bank.

They used the χ^2 distribution technique to compare each of the resulting histograms from the training set with all the learned histogram models from the training set and reported 75.5% accuracy. Bovis and Singh [5] reported a classification accuracy of 71.4% by combining different classifiers in conjunction with the Fourier and Discrete Wavelet Transforms, and first and second-order statistical features. Recently, we have investigated other variants of the LBP [12] operator such as the LTP [14] and LQP [13] operators, which have produced accuracies of up to 82% and 86%, respectively based on multi-resolution and multi-orientation techniques. Subsequently, we introduced the LSP [1] operator which produced an accuracy of 83% based on a single resolution.

III. METHODOLOGY

As shown in Figure 2, firstly, the breast area is segmented in order to estimate the fibro glandular region of interest (*roi*). To automatically find the breast and pectoral muscle boundaries, we employed our previous method in [16], which is based on a region-based Active Contours and restricted contour growing with edge information.

In this study we calculate the dense tissue within the *roi* only in order to obtain more discriminant features instead of from the entire breast region which is the common approach in the literature. Our motivation is that in most cases the non-*roi* contains mostly fatty tissues regardless of its BI-RADS class, and most dense tissues are located and start to develop within this area. Therefore, extracting texture information from the entire breast region increases the possibility of obtaining redundant texture, which makes the extracted features noisy and less discriminating across BI-RADS classes. Our previous studies using the LTP [14], LQP [13] and LSP [1] operators have shown that extracting texture descriptors from the *roi* produced at least 5% to 7% greater accuracy than classifying BI-RADS classes based on features extracted from the entire breast region. To extract the *roi*, we find w (width of the breast), which is the longest perpendicular distance between the y -axis and the breast boundary. We flip w to 90° to the center of w to form the blue square area of the *roi*.

Subsequently, we apply a median filter of 3×3 sliding window and employ the LSP operators to capture the microstructure information within the *roi*. We select only dominant patterns in the feature space to remove redundant information and employed the Support Vector Machine (SVM) as a classifier.

A. Feature Extraction

This section briefly explains the LBP operator introduced by Ojala *et al.* [12] and its extensions, which are the LTP and LQP operators introduced by Tan and Triggs [14] and Nanni *et al.* [13], respectively. Subsequently, we explain our LSP operator, which was introduced in [1]. All these operators

Figure 2. A general overview of the proposed method

use three different mapping tables namely uniform pattern (*'u2'*), rotation invariant pattern (*'ri'*) and both uniform and rotation invariant patterns (*'riu2'*). In our previous studies [18], [19], [12], we found that *'riu2'* patterns (a combination of *'u2'* and *'ri'* patterns) provide more discriminant features.

The value of the LBP code of the pixel (i, j) is given by:

$$LBP_{(P,R)}(i, j) = \sum_{p=0}^{(P-1)} s(g_p - g_c)2^p \quad (1)$$

where R and P are the radius of the circle that forms the neighbourhood of the operator and the number of pixels in the neighbourhood, respectively. The grey level value of the centre pixel is denoted g_c , and g_p is the grey level value of the p^{th} neighbour. The LBP operator thresholds the neighbouring pixels using a two-value encoding system as shown in Equation 2.

$$s(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & x \geq 0 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The LTP operator uses a three-value encoding technique which thresholds the neighbouring pixels using a constant threshold value (τ_1) as shown in Equation 3.

$$s(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & x > g_c + \tau_1 \\ 0, & g_c - \tau_1 < x < g_c + \tau_1 \\ -1, & x < g_c - \tau_1 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

In contrast, the LQP operator thresholds the neighbouring pixels using a five-value encoding technique (see Equation 4) based on two constant thresholds τ_1 and τ_2 . Subsequently, the LQP code image is split into four binary patterns by considering its positive, zero and negative components. Therefore, the LQP operator encodes an image into five channels but results four binary patterns (from two positive channels ($s(1)$ and $s(2)$), zero channel ($s(0)$) and combined negative channels ($s(-1) \cap s(-2)$)).

$$s(x) = \begin{cases} 2, & x \geq g_c + \tau_2 \\ 1, & g_c + \tau_1 \leq x < g_c + \tau_2 \\ 0, & g_c - \tau_1 \leq x < g_c + \tau_1 \\ -1, & g_c - \tau_2 \leq x < g_c - \tau_1 \\ -2, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

The LSP operator uses a similar approach by thresholding the neighbouring pixels using a seven-value encoding technique (hence the name is septenary) based on three threshold values (τ_1 , τ_2 and τ_3). The value of the LSP code of the pixel (i, j) is given by:

$$LSP_{(P,R)}^{pattern}(i, j) = \sum_{p=0}^{(P-1)} s_{pattern}(g_p)2^p \quad (5)$$

where $pattern \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6\}$ represents six binary patterns by considering its upper-positive, middle-positive, lower-positive, upper-negative, middle-negative and lower-negative components denoted as $s(3)$, $s(2)$, $s(1)$, $s(-1)$, $s(-2)$ and $s(-3)$, respectively, as shown in Equation 6

$$s(x) = \begin{cases} 3, & x \geq g_c + \tau_3 \\ 2, & g_c + \tau_2 \leq x < g_c + \tau_3 \\ 1, & g_c + \tau_1 \leq x < g_c + \tau_2 \\ 0, & g_c - \tau_1 \leq x < g_c + \tau_1 \\ -1, & g_c - \tau_2 \leq x < g_c - \tau_1 \\ -2, & g_c - \tau_3 \leq x < g_c - \tau_2 \\ -3, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Note that LSP encodes an image into seven channels but results in six binary patterns. The LSP code image is split into six binary patterns using the following conditions

$$s_{pattern}(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } s(x) = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5 \text{ or } 6\} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Figure 3 shows an example of an LSP code image split into six binary images which represent local patterns in six channels. Unlike LTP and LQP, where the user has to manually determine threshold values, our previous study [1] introduced an automatic approach by computing the number of neighbours with grey level value $\leq 25^{th}$ percentile of the entire neighbourhood, the number of neighbours with grey level value between 25^{th} and 75^{th} percentile of the entire neighbourhood, and the number of neighbours with grey level value $\geq 75^{th}$ percentile. Subsequently, we sort the values in ascending order to determine the τ_1 , τ_2 and τ_3 values.

Figure 3. Examples of LSP an code image and its local pattern images from different channels. Note that the final histogram feature is a concatenation of six histograms computed from each binary channel.

B. Multi-resolution and Neighbourhood Topology

In this study, multi-resolution refers to the use of different values of the radius R and the number of pixels P of the neighbourhood. Following our previous study [19] we employ three different architectures namely small ($LSP_{(R=5,P=10)}$), medium ($LSP_{(R=7,P=14)}$) and large ($LSP_{(R=9,P=18)}$) resolutions. To extract multiresolution features, we simply concatenate all histograms extracted from each resolution such as $\mathbf{H} = \{H(LSP_{(5,10)}) \cup H(LSP_{(7,14)}) \cup H(LSP_{(9,18)})\}$, where \mathbf{H} represents the histogram of the multi-resolution features.

C. Neighbourhood Topology

To investigate the effects of different neighbourhoods, we employed circle parabola, hyperbola and ellipse topologies (illustrated in Figure 4), where all neighbours (black dots) are distributed equally. The red dot indicates the central point of each topology. We summarise the equation and parameters involved in Table II for each topology.

Figure 4. Semantic representation for different neighbourhood topologies. The red circle represents the central pixel.

Figure 5 shows examples of circle and ellipse topologies in a multi-resolution architecture. The same principles apply for parabola and hyperbola topologies.

D. Dominant Patterns

Due to the large number features, we performed dimensionality reduction by selecting dominant patterns to reduce overlapping textural information. According to Guo *et al.* [17], a set of dominant patterns for an image is the minimum

Table I

PARAMETER DESCRIPTIONS FOR ALL NEIGHBOURHOOD TOPOLOGIES. NOTE THAT a AND b ARE THE SEMIMAJOR AND SEMIMINOR AXIS LENGTHS, AND c IS THE DISTANCE BETWEEN VERTEX AND FOCUS.

Topologies	Equations	Parameters
Circle (ci)	$x^2 + y^2 = R^2$	R is the radius of the circle
Ellipse (el)	$\frac{x^2}{a^2} + \frac{y^2}{b^2} = 1$	a and b are the semi-major and semiminor axis lengths, where $a \neq b$
Parabola (par)	$y = -\frac{1}{c}x^2 + 2c$	c is the distance between vertex and focus
Hyperbola (hy)	$\frac{x^2}{a^2} - \frac{y^2}{b^2} = 1$	a and b are the semi-major and semiminor axis lengths

Figure 5. Multi-resolution architecture for the circle and ellipse topologies. The black and the white dots represent pixels which have lower and higher values than the central pixel, respectively.

set of pattern types which can cover n ($0 < n < 100$) of all patterns of an image. To find the dominant patterns we apply the following procedure. Let $I_1, I_2 \dots I_j$ be images in the training set. Firstly, for each training image we compute the multi-resolution histogram feature ($H_{I_j}^{LSP}$). Next, a bin-wise summation procedure was performed for all the histograms to find the distribution of pattern from the training set. Subsequently, the resulting histogram (H) is sorted in descending order, and the patterns corresponding to the first D bins are selected, where D is computed as:

$$D = \arg \min_N \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N-1} H^{LSP}(i)}{\sum_{i=1}^{2^P} H^{LSP}(i)} > 0.01 \times n \quad (8)$$

N and n are the total number of patterns and the threshold value, respectively. Setting $n = 90$ means removing patterns which have less than 10% occurrence in H .

E. Classification

In this study, we employed the SVM classifier using a polynomial kernel. To find the best two parameters (complexity (C) and exponent (e)) of SVM we used the Grid-Search technique. A range of values of C ($C = 1, 2, 3 \dots 10$) and e ($e = 1, 2, 3 \dots 5$ with interval 1.0) was tested. We selected the best combination of C and e based on the highest accuracy in the training phase.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

To test the performance of the LSP operator, we used the MIAS dataset [15]. It consists of 322 mediolateral-oblique (MLO) mammograms taken from 161 women with the following BI-RADS distribution: 60, 105, 129 and 31 for BI-RADS I, II, III and IV, respectively. To further investigate the performance of the LSP operator, we used the InBreast dataset [20] which consists of 206 MLO mammograms of 103 women, with the following BI-RADS distribution: 69, 74, 49 and 14 for BI-RADS I, II, III and IV, respectively. Each image was annotated by an expert radiologist. A stratified ten runs 10-fold cross validation scheme was employed, where the patients were randomly split into 90% for training and 10% for testing, and repeated 100 times. Accuracy (Acc) is used to measure the performance of the method, which represents the total number of correctly classified images as a proportion of the total number of images.

A. Quantitative Results

Table II shows quantitative results using different neighbourhood topologies on both single and multi-resolution techniques. It can be observed that using the multi-resolution technique tends to produce higher accuracy than classification based on features extracted using a single resolution. The $MultiLSP^{el}$ (multi-resolution operator) produced the highest classification accuracy of 86.9%, which is 1.3% higher than $MultiLSP^{ci}$ on the MIAS dataset. On the same dataset, the $MultiLSP^{par}$ produced just under 80% classification accuracy whereas the $MultiLSP^{hy}$ produced over 81%. For the InBreast dataset both $MultiLSP^{ci}$ and $MultiLSP^{el}$ operators produced over 80% classification accuracy. The LSP^{ci} operator produced the best accuracy of 83.3% and 79.3% on the MIAS and InBreast datasets, respectively, using the parameters $R = 9, P = 18$. However, the performance accuracy decreased significantly when smaller values of R and P were used particularly on the InBreast dataset.

The ellipse topology (LSP^{el}) produced the best accuracy for both datasets across different resolutions. The $LSP_{(9,18)}^{el}$ achieved 83.9% and 80.7% accuracies for the MIAS and InBreast datasets, respectively. Using smaller values of R and P produced similar accuracies, which indicates that the ellipse topology is consistent and robust compared to the other topologies. Although the hyperparabola topology ($LSP_{(9,18)}^{hy}$) produced a maximum accuracy of 80.6% on the MIAS dataset, which is 2.7% lower than the accuracy produced by the $LSP_{(9,18)}^{ci}$, on average the LSP^{hy} operator produced consistent performance across different datasets, values of R and P . The parabola topology (LSP^{par}) produced the worst performance compared to the other operators, with a maximum accuracy of 78.1%.

Table II
QUANTITATIVE RESULTS MEASURED IN $Acc(\%)$.

Operators	MIAS	n	InBreast	n
$LSP_{(5,10)}^{ci}$	79.2 \pm 7.1	93.7	76.1 \pm 7.9	98.1
$LSP_{(7,14)}^{ci}$	79.8 \pm 7.1	93.7	74.8 \pm 11.9	98.1
$LSP_{(9,18)}^{ci}$	83.3 \pm 8.8	99.1	79.3 \pm 8.6	92.7
$LSP_{(5,10)}^{el}$	79.9 \pm 8.5	94.1	79.6 \pm 9.6	96.1
$LSP_{(7,14)}^{el}$	80.8 \pm 7.7	95.3	80.4 \pm 8.7	97.5
$LSP_{(9,18)}^{el}$	83.9 \pm 8.8	93.9	80.7 \pm 10.9	97.9
$LSP_{(5,10)}^{par}$	77.6 \pm 9.5	95.5	76.6 \pm 9.1	95.4
$LSP_{(7,14)}^{par}$	78.1 \pm 9.3	96.9	77.9 \pm 8.1	95.9
$LSP_{(9,18)}^{par}$	76.7 \pm 9.6	97.7	74.8 \pm 9.7	94.1
$LSP_{(5,10)}^{hy}$	78.9 \pm 8.8	93.8	77.1 \pm 7.1	92.1
$LSP_{(7,14)}^{hy}$	79.6 \pm 8.1	95.1	78.5 \pm 8.4	95.4
$LSP_{(9,18)}^{hy}$	80.6 \pm 9.3	97.8	78.7 \pm 9.5	97.5
$MultiLSP^{ci}$	85.6 \pm 7.8	93.3	80.2 \pm 8.8	93.9
$MultiLSP^{el}$	86.9 \pm 8.1	94.1	82.6 \pm 8.2	94.1
$MultiLSP^{par}$	79.6 \pm 8.7	95.5	77.4 \pm 7.8	91.5
$MultiLSP^{hy}$	81.4 \pm 8.3	94.9	79.6 \pm 9.1	93.1

B. Quantitative Comparison

Table III shows quantitative results for the other local pattern operators (e.g. LBP, LTP and LQP) when employed using a multi-resolution technique across different topologies. It can be observed that the $MultiLSP^{el}$ produced the highest accuracies of 86.9% and 82.6% for the MIAS and InBreast datasets, respectively. The $MultiLQP^{ci}$ produced classification accuracy of 84.7% on the MIAS dataset but the ellipse topology ($MultiLQP^{el}$) outperformed its performance by 2% on the InBreast dataset. The $MultiLTP^{el}$ outperformed the other topologies on both datasets, whereas when using the multi-resolution technique on LBP, the $MultiLBP^{ci}$ produced the highest accuracies on both datasets.

V. DISCUSSION

Based on our experimental results, using a multi-resolution technique increased the accuracy of breast density classification regardless of the neighbourhood topology. This might be due to the fact that not all texture information can be captured in a single resolution because the size or morphological appearance of the dense tissue vary across different patients. Therefore, the multi-resolution technique extracts texture information that is not available or less effective at any one particular resolution but more discriminating when extracted using a larger resolution.

In terms of the performance of neighbourhood topologies, we found that the circle and ellipse produced higher classification accuracy than the hyperbola and parabola. This might be due to the morphology for most dense tissue within

Table III
QUANTITATIVE COMPARISON WITH MULTI-RESOLUTION LBP, LTP AND LQP

Operators	MIAS	n	InBreast	n
$MultiLBP^{ci}$	73.6 \pm 7.8	99.3	71.2 \pm 7.3	99.9
$MultiLBP^{el}$	72.9 \pm 8.1	99.9	70.6 \pm 7.1	99.3
$MultiLBP^{par}$	68.8 \pm 8.7	99.5	65.4 \pm 7.6	99.2
$MultiLBP^{hy}$	70.4 \pm 8.3	99.9	68.8 \pm 7.3	99.3
$MultiLTP^{ci}$	81.1 \pm 7.4	96.1	77.3 \pm 7.9	95.1
$MultiLTP^{el}$	81.9 \pm 7.1	94.6	77.6 \pm 7.8	95.8
$MultiLTP^{par}$	76.6 \pm 9.7	95.7	73.4 \pm 8.1	96.3
$MultiLTP^{hy}$	77.4 \pm 8.9	96.9	74.6 \pm 9.6	97.1
$MultiLQP^{ci}$	84.7 \pm 7.5	93.3	80.1 \pm 9.1	94.4
$MultiLQP^{el}$	83.3 \pm 8.7	94.1	82.1 \pm 8.2	99.7
$MultiLQP^{par}$	82.6 \pm 7.8	95.5	78.5 \pm 8.8	99.9
$MultiLQP^{hy}$	77.4 \pm 9.3	94.9	78.1 \pm 9.3	99.9
$MultiLSP^{ci}$	85.6 \pm 7.8	93.3	80.2 \pm 8.8	93.9
$MultiLSP^{el}$	86.9 \pm 8.1	94.1	82.6 \pm 8.2	94.1
$MultiLSP^{par}$	79.6 \pm 8.7	95.5	77.4 \pm 7.8	91.5
$MultiLSP^{hy}$	81.4 \pm 8.3	94.9	79.6 \pm 9.1	93.1

the fibroglandular region (roi) being in a ‘round-ish’ shape, which makes these topologies more effective to extract local information. For example, the parabola architecture does not take account the upper neighbouring pixels. Similarly, the hyperparabola architecture only takes account of left and right neighbouring pixels but ignores the upper and lower pixels.

As for the texture operators, experimental results show that the LSP operator tends to outperform the others. Our previous studies [1], [19], [18] found that dividing the code image into several binary channels enable us to capture finer texture information that cannot be captured using the conventional LBP operator. Similar studies of Tan and Triggs [14] and Nanni *et al.* [13] also found that micro texture can be enriched using a multi-channel approach by dividing the code image into different binary channels.

The main limitation of dividing the code image into several binary channels is that it increases the number of features, which means that it increases the amount of redundant information. In our study, we minimised this risk by selecting dominant patterns only during the classification. However, this does not fully solve the problem when two similar features both occur frequently.

VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we have studied the use of the LSP operator for breast density classification using a multi-resolution approach with various neighbourhood topologies. Experimental results show that a multi-resolution approach tends to

produce higher classification accuracy than a single resolution. We have also investigated the role of other topologies, namely ellipse, parabola and hyperbola, and experimental results indicate that the ellipse topology produces higher accuracies across different datasets.

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